

Original Article

Internet Addiction, Academic Procrastination and Self-Esteem among University Students

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Abstract

This study aims to examine Internet Addiction, Academic procrastination, and Self-esteem among university students. The correlational research design was employed, a sample of (N=453) university students of the age range (18-26) selected from public and private universities through purposive sampling. The Descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation were run to assess the frequency, percentage, and demographic variables, The Pearson Product Moment correlation was employed to assess the relationship between study variables. Furthermore, Mediation analysis was carried out to assess the mediating role of academic procrastination between internet addiction and self-esteem by process through Hays. The results revealed that Internet Addiction has significantly positive relationship with Procrastination and Self-esteem. Procrastination has significantly positive relationship Self-esteem. The result of the mediation analysis showed that Internet Addiction significantly and positively predicts Self-esteem. Moreover, Procrastination significantly and positively predicts Self-esteem. Lastly, the interaction between Internet Addiction and Procrastination shows significant prediction of Self-esteem

Keywords: Internet Addiction, Academic Procrastination, Self Esteem

Introduction

Internet addiction has become increasingly prevalent which effects various aspects of life such as Academic performance. With internet access exceeding 40% of the global population and the continuous growth in smartphone usage, this issue is attracting increasing concern. It is characterized by excessive and uncontrolled use of electronic devices, internet addiction can disrupt students' academic focus and responsibilities. The widespread popularity of engaging oneself in online activities like gaming, social media further intensifies the complexity of the problem, especially in the student population who are more prone to develop these addictive behaviors (Salarvand et al., 2022).

The connection between internet addiction and academic procrastination presents a significant challenge for students in this digitalized world. As the internet becomes a primary source of entertainment and social engagement, students may begin to use it as a way to delay academic activities and responsibilities. This pattern of behavior is especially prevalent among individuals facing mental health challenges or low self-esteem, who often resort to the online platforms as a coping mechanism to escape academic pressures. Engaging themselves in this avoiding behavior fosters the perpetuating cycle of procrastination. May offer temporary relief but ultimately contributes to decline in academic performance. . it also increases stress and emotional disturbances, further putting student in a loop that impairs both their wellbeing and academic achievement (Zhang et al., 2022).

Combating the negative impacts pf internet addiction and academic procrastination required a comprehensive and well-rounded strategy that combines education, therapeutic intervention and institutional support and backing.

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Teaching students about the importance of accountability of internet use and the probable long-term consequences of excessive screen time, this plays a vital role in building self-awareness and encouraging thoughtful choices. At the same time implementing evidence-based interventions such as cognitive behavioral therapy and organized digital detox initiatives can equip students with practical strategies to enhance their behavior of digital engagement develop healthier lifestyle routine. Just as essential is the development of a supportive academic atmosphere that emphasizes mental health, emotional strength and deeper psychological causes, this approach can effectively reduce the occurrence and effects of these issues, ultimately improving students' academic success and mental wellbeing (Király et al., 2019).

To summarize, internet addiction and academic procrastination are interrelated factors which can profoundly affect student's academic outcomes and mental health. Identifying this crucial relationship between these factors is critical for developing effective, research-informed interventions. By integrating educational awareness, psychological support and institutional policies, educators and decision makers can help students cultivate balanced digital habits, improve time management and strengthen emotional resilience. Ultimately, such multidimensional approach not only enhance students' mental wellbeing in the current increasingly digital academic environment (Svartdal & Løkke, 2022).

Hypotheses

- There is likely to be a positive relationship between internet addiction and academic procrastination among university students.
- There is likely to be a negative relationship between internet addiction and self-esteem among university students.
- There is likely to be a negative relationship between academic procrastination and self-esteem among university students.
- Academic procrastination is likely to mediate a relationship between internet addiction and self-esteem among university students.
- There are gender differences in internet addiction, academic procrastination, and self-esteem among university students.

Method

Research design

The correlation research design was employed to assess the relationship between internet addiction, academic procrastination and self-esteem among university students.

Participants

The Purposive sampling was employed to select (N=453) students from various public and private sectors in Lahore, Pakistan. The sample size was determined using G-power. The selected participants included 51% boys and 48% girls, aged between 18 and 26 years (Mage = 22.2, SD= 8.3). Only those participants were included who have a smartphone and regularly use the internet for more than one hour. Individuals with any physical or mental disabilities were excluded as assessed through a demographic questionnaire.

Measures

Demographic sheet

The demographic questionnaire included details about participants' age, gender, educational institution, level of education, birth order, number of siblings, marital status, socioeconomic status, family structure, relationships with parents and siblings, number of close friends, time spent with close friends, hours spent using technology, and presence of any physical or mental disabilities.

Internet Addiction Scale (Mathivanan, 2022)

The Internet Addiction Scale was developed by Mathivanan in 2022 and comprises 10 items. It designed on a 4-point Likert-type scale ranging from 0 (never) to 3. The scale focuses on three main criteria: withdrawal (items 1, 6, 7), loss of control (items 2, 3, 4, 5, 8), and impairment in functioning (items 9, 10). Participants responded to statements regarding their internet usage over the past month, indicating the frequency of agreement with each

statement. Higher scores on the scale indicate higher levels of internet addiction. The test-retest reliability was found to be 0.85, and internal consistency ranged from $\alpha = 0.90$ to 0.93. The current test-retest reliability of the Internet Addiction Scale is 0.86 (Mathivanan, 2022)

Academic procrastination (McCloskey, 2015)

The Academic Procrastination Scale (APS) was developed by McCloskey in 2015. It comprises 25 items and has demonstrated strong reliability, with a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of .95. Currently, the test-retest reliability stands at .93. Respondents rated each item on a 5-point Likert-type scale, ranging from 1 (disagree) to 5 (agree). For instance, agreeing with statements such as "I put off projects until the last minute" suggests a higher level of procrastination. The scale evaluates students' routines and habits to gauge their tendency to procrastinate in academic settings. Notably, items 1, 8, 12, 14, and 25 are reverse-scored. The total scores ranging from 25 to 125, with a mean score of 72. Scores falling between 25 and 75 suggest low levels of procrastination behavior among students, while scores ranging from 76 to 125 indicate higher levels of procrastination behavior (McCloskey, 2015)

Self-Esteem Scale (Morris Rosenberg, 1965)

The Self-esteem scale, developed by Morris Rosenberg in 1965, comprises ten items aimed at assessing overall self-worth through the evaluation of both positive and negative self-perceptions. The scale is considered to be one-dimensional. Each item is rated on a 4-point Likert scale, with 1 representing "strongly agree," 2 for "agree," 3 for "disagree," and 4 for "strongly disagree." Items 2, 5, 6, 8, and 9 are reverse-scored. Higher scores indicate greater levels of self-esteem. The RSE demonstrates exceptional internal consistency, with a Guttman scale coefficient of reliability of .92. Moreover, the correlations between tests are .85 and .88, indicating high stability. The current test-retest reliability of this scale stands at .66 (Morris Rosenberg, 1965)

Procedure

The study was initiated by taking institutional permission for conducting the research. Then the permission to use the scales was taken from the authors via e-mail. A sample consisting of N=453 participants was recruited from Higher Education Commission recognized public and private sector institutes in Lahore. Prior to the main study, a pilot study was carried out with a sample size of N=20 participants to evaluate factors such as language comprehension, willingness of participants to engage in the study, and the time required for questionnaire completion. The questionnaire took approximately 10 minutes to complete, with participants demonstrating good comprehension of the language used and indicating feasibility regarding the scales. The participants were acknowledged for their participation in the study. The pilot study data was further added in the main analysis. For the conduction of the main study, the participants were informed about the aims and objectives of the current study and their consent to participate in the study was taken. Participants were also informed about their willingness to participate in the research and their right to withdraw from the research at any time. Furthermore, the participants were informed that their confidentiality will be maintained and their identity will not reveal. The Confidentiality regarding the information of the participants was guaranteed by recording the data in the form of codes in the SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences). It took almost two months to complete the data and 10 minutes to complete the google form. There was 218 from the public sector and 235 from the private sector. Online data were collected d 3.7

Operational Definition

Internet Addiction: Internet addiction is characterized by uncontrollable urges or behaviors related to internet use, leading individuals to procrastinate on daily tasks and resulting in poor academic and job performance

Academic Procrastination: Academic procrastination refers to the habit of postponing or delaying school-related tasks and responsibilities. This behavior is observed in students of various ages, spanning from grade school to those pursuing higher education or degrees.

Self Esteem: Self-esteem encompasses one's beliefs about oneself, which can be either positive or negative. It serves as a crucial personal asset for coping with stress and preserving health. Individuals with high self-esteem view themselves positively and take pride in their accomplishments, whereas those with low self-esteem often feel worthless and lack confidence

Ethical Consideration

The student followed the ethical consideration of American Psychological Association.

- Institutional approval was obtained from the department of Professional Psychology Bahria University to conduct the study
- The permission from the authors of assessment measures was obtained.
- Written informed consent of participants was obtained ensuring confidentiality voluntary participants and write to with draw from research.
- Participants were provided necessary information about nature and purpose through information sheet.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 21.0 was used to analyze the data. Descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation were run to assess the frequency, percentage, and demographic variables, The Pearson Product Moment correlation was employed to assess the relationship between study variables. Furthermore, Mediation analysis was carried out to assess the mediating role of academic procrastination between internet addiction and self-esteem by process through Hays

Results

Table 1

Demographic Characteristics of the Sample (N=453)

Variables	F%	M(SD)
Age		2.2(.83)
Age category		
18-20	120(26.5)	
21-23	124(27.4)	
24-26	209(46.1)	
Gender		
Male	220(48.6)	
Female	233(51.4)	
Education		
MSc/ MS	148(32.7)	
BS(Hons)	305(67.3)	
University		
Public	218(48.1)	
Private	235(51.9)	

Which social media platform does you use the most?

WhatsApp	31(14.1)
Facebook	32(14.5)
Instagram	23(10.5)
OtherApps	134(60.7)

Which social media platform does Females use the most?

WhatsApp	41(17.6)
Facebook	57(24.5)
Instagram	70(30.0)
OtherApps	62(26.1)

Note: M=mean; SD=standard deviation; f=frequency

Table 1 shows demographic characteristics of the sample, the age Mean=2.2 and SD=.83. Most of the participants are 24-26 years of age and 51.4 percent of them are females. Most of them are the undergraduate students from which 51.9 percent are from private university. percent of the Males spent their most time on other apps like snapchat,

skype and Netflix whereas 70 percent of the females have reported Instagram as the mostly used platform on social media. 60.5 percent of Males spend more than 10 hours on social media whereas 34.3 percent of females spend 1-3 hours on social media which means males spend more time on social media as compared to females.

Table 2
Psychometric Properties of Scales and Subscales (N= 453)

Variables	K	M	SD	<i>a</i>	Range	Skewness	Kurtosis
Potential Actual							
Internet Addiction	10	22.87	5.20	.86	10-30	-.55	-.66
Procrastination	25	73.47	19.27	.93	29-114	.12	-1.39
Self-esteem	10	19.55	4.27	.66	11-37	.95	1.14

Note. M= mean, SD= standard deviation, K= No. of items

The above table shows the psychometric properties and reliability coefficients of three measures i.e., Internet Addiction Score is M=22.87 with SD=5.20, skewness range is -.55 which is within the normal range of +2 -2 and the reliability value is .86. Mean of the Procrastination score is M=73.47 with SD=19.27, skewness range is .12 and the reliability coefficient value is .93. The mean score of Self-esteem is M=19.55 with SD=4.27, skewness range is .95 the reliability coefficient is .66

Table 3
Correlation between Demographic Variables, Internet Addiction, Academic Procrastination and Self-Esteem (n=453).

Variable	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5
Age	2.20	.83	-	-.03	-.30***	-.47***	-.13**
Male	1.51	.50					
Female	1.51	.50	-	-	-.22***	.13**	.08
Internet Addiction	22.87	5.20	-	-	-	.53***	.13**
Procrastination	73.47	19.27	-	-	-	-	.42***
Self-esteem	19.54	4.27	-	-	-	-	-

Note, M=mean, SD=Standard Deviation.

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). * Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed) **
*=p<.05, **=p<.01, ***=p<.001

The results show that Age has a significantly negative relationship with Internet Addiction (-.30***), Procrastination (-.47***) and Self-esteem (-.13**). This indicates that when age increases internet addiction, procrastination and self-esteem significantly decreases. Gender also shows significantly negative relationship with Internet Addiction (.22***) which indicates that Males (M=24.05; SD=4.87) has more Internet Addiction as compared to Females (M=21.76; SD=5.25). Gender has significantly positive relationship with procrastination (.13**) which indicates that Females (M=75.85; SD=17.72) have more Procrastination as compared to Males (M=70.85; SD=20.63). There were no significant gender differences in terms of Self-esteem. Internet Addiction has significantly positive relationship with Procrastination (.53***) and Self-esteem (.13**) which indicates that when internet addiction increases Procrastination and Self-esteem also increases. Lastly Procrastination has significantly positive relationship Self- esteem (.42***) which indicates that when Procrastination Increases Self-esteem also increases.

Table 4
Mediation Through PROCESS Indicating the Interaction effect of Internet Addiction and Procrastination on Self-Esteem among University Students (N=453).

Variables	B	95% CI for B		SE B	R	R ²
		LL	UL			
Step 1					.65***	.42***
Constant	36.10	25.77	46.43	5.25		
Internet Addiction	1.77	1.48	2.05	.14		
Age	-7.38	-9.10	-5.66	.87		

Gender	8.64	5.86	11.42	1.41		
Step 2					.44***	.19***
Constant	12.63	9.77	15.48	1.45		
Procrastination	.11	.09	.14	.01		
Internet Addiction	-.11	-.19	-.02	.04		
Age	.42	-.07	.90	.24		
Gender	-.12	-.88	.63	.38		
Step 3					.19***	.03***
constant	16.88	13.91	19.85	1.51		
Internet Addiction	.10	.02	.18	.04		
Age	-.44	-.94	.04	.25		
Gender	.89	.09	1.69	.40		

Note: *= $p < .05$, **= $p < .01$, ***= $p < .001$

In the first step internet addiction was added keeping age and gender as constant and the model accounted for 42% variance on Self-Esteem with $F(1, 451) = 112.14, p < .001$. In the second step procrastination was added where age and gender again remains constant and the model accounted for 19% of variance with $F(2, 450) = 27.41, p > .05$. In the final step the total effect was calculated and the model accounted for 3% of variance with $F(1, 451) = 5.40, p < .05$. The overall model accounted for 64% of variance on Self-esteem. The result of the mediation analysis showed that Internet Addiction significantly and positively predicts Self-esteem. Moreover, Procrastination significantly and positively predicts Self-esteem. Lastly, the interaction between Internet Addiction and Procrastination shows significant prediction of Self-esteem.

Table 4

Independent Sample t- test Comparing Gender Difference in term of Internet Addiction, Procrastination and Self-Esteem (N=453).

Variables	Male (n= 220)		Female (n=233)		t=(452)	p	Cohen's d
M	SD		M		SD		
Internet Addiction	24.05	4.87	21.76	5.25	4.79	.001	.45
P	70.85	20.53	75.85	17.72	-2.72	.001	.26
SE	19.19	4.33	19.88	4.19	-1.71	.19	.16

Note. M= mean, SD= standard deviation

The assumption of homogeneity of variance was found to be assumed for Self-esteem; $F = 1.65, p < .05$, Internet Addiction; $F = 11.39, p > .05$, Procrastination; $F = 11.40, p > .05$. The results of independent sample t- test showed that there was significant gender difference in terms of Internet Addiction and Procrastination. Males ($M = 24.05$; $SD = 4.87$) have more Internet Addiction as compared to females ($M = 21.76$; $SD = 5.25$). Whereas Females ($M = 75.85$; $SD = 17.72$) have more Procrastination than Males ($M = 70.85$; $SD = 20.63$). The results also showed that there was non-significant gender difference in terms of Self-Esteem.

Discussion

The study aimed to investigate the interplay between Internet Addiction, Academic Procrastination, and Self-esteem among university students. Conducted as a correlational study with 453 participants, the findings shed light on various aspects of social media usage and its implications. Results indicated that males tended to spend more time on social media platforms like Twitter and LinkedIn, potentially for career-related purposes, while females showed a preference for Instagram, likely driven by interests in fashion and self-expression.

Interestingly, age emerged as a factor influencing internet addiction, procrastination, and self-esteem. Older individuals generally reported lower level of internet addiction and academic procrastination. Potentially due to greater life experiences, maturity and increased personal or professional responsibility that demand more structured time management. However, a decline in self-esteem was noted with increasing age, which may be influenced by age-related physical changes and devolving perceptions of identity and self-worth (Sechi & Cabras, 2021).

Gender differences also emerged as noteworthy. Males demonstrated higher levels of internet addiction, possibly due to greater inclination toward online gaming or digital engagement. In contrast, females unexpectedly

exhibited higher levels of procrastination. The desire to perform tasks flawlessly might result in delays and difficulty initiating academic or personal responsibilities (Mo et al., 2020).

The study also shed light on the critical interconnection between internet addiction, procrastination and self-esteem. Finding revealed a positive correlation between internet addiction and both procrastination and self-esteem, suggesting that excessive internet usage can negatively affect negatively academic outcomes and psychological health.

Additionally, mediation analysis indicated that procrastination partially mediated the relationship between self-esteem and internet addiction. This implied that habitual delay in academic tasks, often fueled by excessive social media use, may foster feelings of guilt and inadequacy, thereby diminishing self-esteem.

In conclusion, the study emphasizes the need to explore the nuanced connections between digital behavior, academic habits and psychological well-being among university students offering meaningful direction for future research and targeted interventions.

Conclusion

The study explored the relationship between university students' internet usage, academic procrastination and self-esteem. The findings revealed that students who spend more time online are more likely to engage in procrastination and exhibit different levels of self-esteem. Age and gender were also significant factors, with older students and male participants demonstrating distinct behavioral patterns compared to their younger and female counterparts. Interestingly, while there were differences between genders in internet use and procrastination, there wasn't a big difference in how they felt about themselves. Our analysis also showed that spending too much time online and delaying tasks both contribute to how students feel about themselves. This study helps us understand how internet use, procrastination, and self-esteem are connected among university students, which could be helpful for creating support programs tailored to their needs.

Strengths

- The constructs internet addiction, procrastination and self-esteem are closely related to the psychological wellbeing of the students. So by investigating their relationship we can gain insight into the factors that effects the mental health of the students and hence devising certain interventions to improve their wellbeing.
- Furthermore, for the students who struggle in the life to manage their time and involve in internet addiction and end up delaying their work, our research can bring attention to them that how important time management is and its association with procrastination and self-esteem.
- With increasing age internet addiction is decreasing so it is assumed that adolescent have higher internet addiction as compared to our sample. which is a highly sensitive age. So we should target that population in future research and devise safe internet usage and Intervention plans for them. Because these are academic years. So our study highlights that school counselors should provide information to the students for safe internet usage plans.
- we need to find out whether the males are using internet as a coping mechanism to save themselves from the stressors of daily life and anxiety and depression. Therefore, we need to make certain apps that helps males to get help for mental health issues.

Limitations

There are some limitations of this research.

- The sample was quite homogenous i.e., the participants that take part in the research and are easily accessible are the undergraduates from some main universities and same city so the results are difficult to generalize.
- We cannot find differences in self-esteem of the males and females. Since there are different domains of self-esteem that needs to be measured separately to find our differences in self-esteem like social, physical and academic self-esteem.

Recommendations

- A larger sample should be used in the future to make the research more generalizable.
- The future researches should use a diverse sample and population that will include all government and private universities all across the Pakistan to get generalizable results.

- Qualitative research should also be conducted among these variables to get more accurate results.

Implications

- This research brings awareness among young adults regarding how to improve their self-esteem by managing their time effectively instead of wasting their time on internet.
- It also creates awareness about the fact that academic procrastination or delaying your tasks continuously can only lead towards stress and anxiety about the future tasks and outcomes.
- Academic procrastination and low self-esteem can affect individuals' productivity and performance in educational settings. By identifying factors that contribute to procrastination and low self-esteem, researchers can develop strategies to enhance productivity, time management skills, and self-confidence.
- From the present result we found out that students become victim of internet addiction because they lack social connections and bonding within the family. So we should create awareness to work to improve the social connections within the family members.

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